

Annex and Supplementary material for:

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Annex

Measurement model: Variables and items

Code	Variables/Items
SC-Ag	SC AGILITY
Agil11	The following applications communicate in real time: Supply chain applications with internal applications in our organization (such as enterprise resource planning).
Agil12	The following applications communicate in real time: Customer relationship applications with internal applications in our company.
Agil21	Our customers choose us because we deliver flexibly for their needs.
Agil22	Our company strives to shorten supplier lead time in order to prevent inventory and stockouts.
Agil23	Flexibility in response to requests for changes is a characteristic of our relationships with our key suppliers.
Agil31	We can add product variety without sacrificing quality.
Agil32	We can easily add significant product variety without increasing cost.
Agil33	Our capability for responding quickly to customization requirements is very high.
SC-Ad	SC ADAPTABILITY
Adapt11	Our production system is designed to accommodate changes in demand volume.
Adapt12	Our production system is designed to accommodate changes in the production mix.
Adapt21	We have a good understanding of where our production technology stands in terms of technology life cycles.
Adapt22	Our plant stays on the leading edge of new technology in our industry.
Adapt31	We monitor economies around the world to detect potential new markets.
Adapt32	We are concerned about the needs of both our immediate customers and our end consumers.
Adapt33	We monitor economies around the world to find potential new suppliers.
Adapt34	We have a very good understanding of our suppliers' distribution processes.
SC-AI	SC ALIGNMENT
Align11	Our top managers repeatedly tell us that sharing supply chain risks and rewards with our customers is critical to our plant's success.
Align12	Our top managers repeatedly tell us that sharing supply chain risks and rewards with our suppliers is critical to our plant's success.
Align13	Our supply chain members have clearly defined goals in our supply chain.
Align21	We emphasize openness of communication in collaboration with our customers.
Align22	We emphasize openness of communication in collaboration with our suppliers.
Align24	We use unambiguous language and communication with our supply chain partners.
Align31	Cooperating with our customers is beneficial to us.
Align32	Cooperating with our suppliers is beneficial to us.
Align33	Our supply chain partners understand our manufacturing capabilities.
CA	COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE
	Please, rate your plant compared to its competitors in the same industry
GLOBLX03	On-time delivery performance.
GLOBLX04	Fast delivery.
GLOBLX05	Flexibility to change product mix.
GLOBLX06	Flexibility to change volume.
GLOBLX08	Cycle time (from raw materials to delivery).
	Control Variables
Industry Dummy	Industry (electronics reference category)
Ind2	Dummy variable. Takes value 1 for Machinery, 0 in rest of cases
Ind3	Dummy variable. Takes value 1 for automotive components, 0 in rest of cases
	Country context
Emerging/developed	Dummy variable. Takes value 1 for Plants in developed countries, 0 in emerging countries
	Plant size
LogPlantSize	Log number of employees in the plant

Appendix A.

Examples of prediction error distributions

Appendix B. Descriptive statistics by sample

B1.- Descriptive statistics DRM model

	M1				M2				M3				M4				M5			
	Mean	Min	Max	Std. dev.	Mean	Min	Max	Std. dev.	Mean	Min	Max	Std. dev.	Mean	Min	Max	Std. dev.	Mean	Min	Max	Std. dev.
CA	3.792	1.000	5.000	0.644	3.794	1.000	5.000	0.643	3.799	1.000	5.000	0.640	3.793	1.000	5.000	0.653	3.801	1.000	5.000	0.644
SC-Ad	3.799	2.111	5.000	0.488	3.810	2.326	5.000	0.487	3.800	2.233	5.000	0.483	3.815	2.132	5.000	0.487	3.799	2.019	5.000	0.494
SC-Ag	3.823	1.682	4.889	0.468	3.832	1.649	4.917	0.473	3.810	1.645	4.892	0.480	3.863	1.686	4.957	0.484	3.813	1.677	4.903	0.476
SC-AI	4.097	2.867	5.000	0.420	4.093	2.849	5.000	0.418	4.060	2.524	5.000	0.437	4.108	2.872	5.000	0.415	4.092	2.867	5.000	0.422

B2.- Correlations DRM model for each dataset

MI1	CA	SC-Ad	SC-Ag	SC-AI
CA	1.000	0.333	0.318	0.301
SC-Ad	0.333	1.000	0.607	0.552
SC-Ag	0.318	0.607	1.000	0.485
SC-AI	0.301	0.552	0.485	1.000
MI2	CA	SC-Ad	SC-Ag	SC-AI
CA	1.000	0.359	0.319	0.317
SC-Ad	0.359	1.000	0.615	0.547
SC-Ag	0.319	0.615	1.000	0.469
SC-AI	0.317	0.547	0.469	1.000
MI3	CA	SC-Ad	SC-Ag	SC-AI
CA	1.000	0.364	0.319	0.305
SC-Ad	0.364	1.000	0.605	0.568
SC-Ag	0.319	0.605	1.000	0.489
SC-AI	0.305	0.568	0.489	1.000
MI4	CA	SC-Ad	SC-Ag	SC-AI
CA	1.000	0.350	0.339	0.295
SC-Ad	0.350	1.000	0.601	0.538
SC-Ag	0.339	0.601	1.000	0.482
SC-AI	0.295	0.538	0.482	1.000
MI5	CA	SC-Ad	SC-Ag	SC-AI
CA	1.000	0.339	0.332	0.272
SC-Ad	0.339	1.000	0.602	0.513
SC-Ag	0.332	0.602	1.000	0.456
SC-AI	0.272	0.513	0.456	1.000

Appendix C

DRM Constructs measurement model

Item codes	Original Sample (O) weights	Standard Deviation (ST DEV)	p-Values	Weights LCI 95%	Weights UCI 95%	Original Sample (O) loadings	Standard Deviation (ST DEV)	p-Values	Loadings LCI 95%	Loadings UCI 95%
Adapt11-> SC-Ad	0.243	0,073	0,001	0,101	0,386	0,592	0,081	0,000	0,434	0,750
Adapt12-> SC-Ad	0.318	0,077	0,000	0,168	0,468	0,643	0,079	0,000	0,488	0,797
Adapt21-> SC-Ad	0.203	0,059	0,001	0,087	0,318	0,557	0,074	0,000	0,412	0,702
Adapt22-> SC-Ad	0.210	0,055	0,000	0,100	0,320	0,663	0,061	0,000	0,543	0,783
Adapt31-> SC-Ad	0.221	0,069	0,001	0,086	0,356	0,555	0,091	0,000	0,376	0,734
Adapt32-> SC-Ad	0.270	0,070	0,000	0,131	0,408	0,539	0,090	0,000	0,362	0,716
Adapt33-> SC-Ad	0.138	0,075	0,069	-0,010	0,287	0,403	0,109	0,000	0,189	0,618
Adapt34-> SC-Ad	0.218	0,081	0,008	0,057	0,379	0,335	0,107	0,002	0,124	0,546
Agil11-> SC-Ag	0.091	0,091	0,320	-0,090	0,270	0,317	0,149	0,034	0,024	0,610
Agil12-> SC-Ag	0.113	0,101	0,269	-0,090	0,316	0,354	0,148	0,018	0,061	0,647
Agil21-> SC-Ag	0.258	0,078	0,001	0,106	0,411	0,455	0,101	0,000	0,257	0,653
Agil22-> SC-Ag	0.238	0,082	0,004	0,078	0,398	0,468	0,111	0,000	0,250	0,685
Agil23-> SC-Ag	0.209	0,095	0,028	0,023	0,395	0,417	0,134	0,002	0,154	0,680
Agil31-> SC-Ag	0.276	0,066	0,000	0,146	0,405	0,608	0,080	0,000	0,450	0,765
Agil32-> SC-Ag	0.282	0,087	0,001	0,111	0,452	0,592	0,105	0,000	0,386	0,797
Agil33-> SC-Ag	0.378	0,069	0,000	0,241	0,514	0,731	0,064	0,000	0,606	0,857
Align11-> SC-AI	0.220	0,084	0,009	0,055	0,385	0,439	0,107	0,000	0,229	0,650
Align12-> SC-AI	0.160	0,077	0,039	0,008	0,311	0,468	0,103	0,000	0,266	0,669
Align13-> SC-AI	0.233	0,059	0,000	0,119	0,348	0,674	0,069	0,000	0,538	0,810
Align21-> SC-AI	0.255	0,076	0,001	0,105	0,405	0,618	0,080	0,000	0,460	0,777
Align22-> SC-AI	0.173	0,063	0,007	0,049	0,297	0,598	0,073	0,000	0,455	0,741
Align24-> SC-AI	0.206	0,068	0,003	0,072	0,340	0,556	0,081	0,000	0,398	0,715
Align31-> SC-AI	0.208	0,071	0,004	0,068	0,348	0,511	0,089	0,000	0,337	0,685
Align32-> SC-AI	0.215	0,070	0,002	0,079	0,351	0,609	0,082	0,000	0,449	0,769
Align33-> SC-AI	0.111	0,069	0,110	-0,03	0,247	0,507	0,092	0,000	0,327	0,687
GLOBLX03 <- CA	0.245	0,037	0,000	0,173	0,317	0,700	0,049	0,000	0,604	0,796
GLOBLX04 <- CA	0.290	0,028	0,000	0,235	0,344	0,845	0,021	0,000	0,805	0,885
GLOBLX05 <- CA	0.300	0,036	0,000	0,230	0,371	0,775	0,035	0,000	0,705	0,844
GLOBLX06 <- CA	0.227	0,033	0,000	0,162	0,292	0,761	0,039	0,000	0,685	0,838
GLOBLX08 <- CA	0.237	0,039	0,000	0,161	0,312	0,753	0,039	0,000	0,676	0,831

Bootstrapping based on n = 5000 sub-samples. Multiple imputation overall estimate based on Schafer & Olsen (1998). LCI Lower Confidence interval; UCI Upper confidence interval

DRM CA internal consistency and AVE

CA (PIs)	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
MI1	0.826	0.831	0.878	0.590
MI2	0.825	0.835	0.877	0.589
MI3	0.824	0.833	0.877	0.589
MI4	0.829	0.839	0.880	0.595
MI5	0.825	0.834	0.877	0.589

MRM1 Constructs measurement model

Item codes	Original Sample (O) weights	Standard Deviation (ST DEV)	p-Values	Weights LCI 95%	Weights UCI 95%	Original Sample (O) loadings	Standard Deviation (ST DEV)	p-Values	Loadings LCI 95%	Loadings UCI 95%
Adapt11-> SC-Ad	0.252	0.036	0.000	0.182	0.322	0.592	0.064	0.000	0.467	0.717
Adapt12-> SC-Ad	0.261	0.036	0.000	0.189	0.332	0.598	0.060	0.000	0.480	0.716
Adapt21-> SC-Ad	0.201	0.029	0.000	0.143	0.258	0.558	0.061	0.000	0.438	0.678
Adapt22-> SC-Ad	0.243	0.030	0.000	0.183	0.303	0.683	0.049	0.000	0.587	0.780
Adapt31-> SC-Ad	0.204	0.031	0.000	0.143	0.264	0.536	0.065	0.000	0.409	0.663
Adapt32-> SC-Ad	0.213	0.035	0.000	0.144	0.282	0.485	0.071	0.000	0.345	0.625
Adapt33-> SC-Ad	0.209	0.041	0.000	0.128	0.289	0.471	0.081	0.000	0.312	0.630
Adapt34-> SC-Ad	0.267	0.047	0.000	0.175	0.359	0.395	0.079	0.000	0.240	0.549
Agil11-> SC-Ag	0.128	0.044	0.005	0.041	0.216	0.372	0.093	0.000	0.186	0.557
Agil12-> SC-Ag	0.151	0.045	0.001	0.061	0.240	0.407	0.092	0.000	0.221	0.592
Agil21-> SC-Ag	0.270	0.043	0.000	0.186	0.355	0.467	0.074	0.000	0.321	0.614
Agil22-> SC-Ag	0.228	0.050	0.000	0.130	0.325	0.469	0.090	0.000	0.292	0.645
Agil23-> SC-Ag	0.236	0.058	0.000	0.121	0.351	0.433	0.103	0.000	0.231	0.635
Agil31-> SC-Ag	0.247	0.046	0.000	0.156	0.337	0.583	0.076	0.000	0.435	0.732
Agil32-> SC-Ag	0.305	0.048	0.000	0.211	0.399	0.598	0.075	0.000	0.451	0.744
Agil33-> SC-Ag	0.329	0.041	0.000	0.249	0.408	0.692	0.054	0.000	0.587	0.797
Align11-> SC-AI	0.171	0.043	0.000	0.087	0.255	0.397	0.085	0.000	0.228	0.565
Align12-> SC-AI	0.165	0.031	0.000	0.104	0.227	0.483	0.068	0.000	0.349	0.616
Align13-> SC-AI	0.260	0.030	0.000	0.201	0.320	0.700	0.043	0.000	0.616	0.785
Align21-> SC-AI	0.251	0.035	0.000	0.183	0.319	0.607	0.052	0.000	0.505	0.709
Align22-> SC-AI	0.209	0.031	0.000	0.149	0.269	0.625	0.050	0.000	0.528	0.723
Align24-> SC-AI	0.161	0.029	0.000	0.104	0.218	0.540	0.060	0.000	0.422	0.658
Align31-> SC-AI	0.184	0.034	0.000	0.117	0.252	0.485	0.068	0.000	0.352	0.619
Align32-> SC-AI	0.218	0.032	0.000	0.156	0.281	0.616	0.051	0.000	0.516	0.715
Align33-> SC-AI	0.140	0.028	0.000	0.085	0.195	0.544	0.061	0.000	0.424	0.663
GLOBLX03 <- CA	0.249	0.038	0.000	0.174	0.323	0.703	0.049	0.000	0.608	0.798
GLOBLX04 <- CA	0.290	0.030	0.000	0.231	0.349	0.845	0.021	0.000	0.804	0.887
GLOBLX05 <- CA	0.294	0.037	0.000	0.220	0.368	0.770	0.036	0.000	0.700	0.841
GLOBLX06 <- CA	0.225	0.036	0.000	0.155	0.295	0.759	0.040	0.000	0.680	0.838
GLOBLX08 <- CA	0.242	0.040	0.000	0.164	0.319	0.756	0.038	0.000	0.682	0.831

Bootstrapping based on n = 5000 sub-samples. Multiple imputation overall estimate based on Schafer & Olsen (1998). LCI Lower Confidence interval; UCI Upper confidence interval

MRM1 CA internal consistency and AVE

CA (Pis)	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
MI1	0.826	0.831	0.878	0.590
MI2	0.825	0.833	0.877	0.589
MI3	0.824	0.832	0.877	0.589
MI4	0.829	0.838	0.880	0.595
MI5	0.825	0.832	0.877	0.589

MRM2 Constructs measurement model

Item codes	Original Sample (O) weights	Standard Deviation (ST DEV)	p-Values	Weights LCI 95%	Weights UCI 95%	Original Sample (O) loadings	Standard Deviation (ST DEV)	p-Values	Loadings LCI 95%	Loadings UCI 95%
Adapt11-> SC-Ad	0.322	0.034	0.000	0.256	0.389	0.672	0.050	0.000	0.573	0.770
Adapt12-> SC-Ad	0.311	0.039	0.000	0.235	0.388	0.665	0.052	0.000	0.562	0.768
Adapt21-> SC-Ad	0.214	0.030	0.000	0.155	0.274	0.600	0.058	0.000	0.487	0.713
Adapt22-> SC-Ad	0.273	0.030	0.000	0.214	0.333	0.723	0.040	0.000	0.645	0.802
Adapt31-> SC-Ad	0.169	0.034	0.000	0.101	0.236	0.480	0.075	0.000	0.332	0.627
Adapt32-> SC-Ad	0.155	0.035	0.000	0.085	0.224	0.418	0.079	0.000	0.263	0.573
Adapt33-> SC-Ad	0.150	0.047	0.002	0.057	0.243	0.397	0.095	0.000	0.211	0.582
Adapt34-> SC-Ad	0.161	0.048	0.001	0.067	0.256	0.278	0.092	0.002	0.099	0.458
Agil11-> SC-Ag	0.115	0.045	0.012	0.026	0.204	0.346	0.099	0.001	0.150	0.542
Agil12-> SC-Ag	0.143	0.045	0.002	0.053	0.234	0.400	0.096	0.000	0.207	0.593
Agil21-> SC-Ag	0.251	0.042	0.000	0.169	0.333	0.450	0.072	0.000	0.309	0.591
Agil22-> SC-Ag	0.162	0.044	0.000	0.075	0.249	0.381	0.091	0.000	0.202	0.560
Agil23-> SC-Ag	0.154	0.054	0.004	0.048	0.261	0.335	0.112	0.003	0.115	0.556
Agil31-> SC-Ag	0.278	0.043	0.000	0.194	0.361	0.616	0.068	0.000	0.482	0.750
Agil32-> SC-Ag	0.351	0.043	0.000	0.267	0.434	0.661	0.054	0.000	0.555	0.767
Agil33-> SC-Ag	0.369	0.039	0.000	0.291	0.446	0.736	0.040	0.000	0.658	0.814
Align11-> SC-AI	0.220	0.084	0.009	0.055	0.384	0.439	0.107	0.000	0.229	0.649
Align12-> SC-AI	0.160	0.078	0.040	0.007	0.313	0.468	0.103	0.000	0.266	0.670
Align13-> SC-AI	0.233	0.058	0.000	0.119	0.348	0.674	0.069	0.000	0.538	0.810
Align21-> SC-AI	0.255	0.076	0.001	0.105	0.405	0.619	0.080	0.000	0.461	0.776
Align22-> SC-AI	0.173	0.063	0.007	0.049	0.298	0.598	0.074	0.000	0.453	0.743
Align24-> SC-AI	0.206	0.068	0.003	0.072	0.339	0.556	0.081	0.000	0.397	0.716
Align31-> SC-AI	0.208	0.071	0.004	0.068	0.348	0.511	0.089	0.000	0.338	0.685
Align32-> SC-AI	0.215	0.069	0.002	0.079	0.351	0.609	0.083	0.000	0.447	0.771
Align33-> SC-AI	0.111	0.069	0.109	-0.025	0.247	0.508	0.093	0.000	0.325	0.690
GLOBLX03 <- CA	0.245	0.038	0.000	0.169	0.320	0.700	0.049	0.000	0.605	0.795
GLOBLX04 <- CA	0.290	0.029	0.000	0.233	0.346	0.845	0.021	0.000	0.803	0.887
GLOBLX05 <- CA	0.297	0.037	0.000	0.224	0.370	0.773	0.036	0.000	0.702	0.844
GLOBLX06 <- CA	0.229	0.035	0.000	0.160	0.298	0.762	0.040	0.000	0.684	0.840
GLOBLX08 <- CA	0.239	0.040	0.000	0.160	0.318	0.755	0.039	0.000	0.678	0.832

Bootstrapping based on n = 5000 sub-samples. Multiple imputation overall estimate based on Schafer & Olsen (1998). LCI Lower Confidence interval; UCI Upper confidence interval

MRM2 CA internal consistency and AVE

CA (PIs)	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
MI1	0.826	0.831	0.878	0.591
MI2	0.825	0.834	0.877	0.589
MI3	0.824	0.832	0.877	0.589
MI4	0.829	0.838	0.880	0.595
MI5	0.825	0.833	0.877	0.589

Appendix D.

DRM model PLS predict assessment for full sample of each multiple imputation dataset (MI1 to MI5).
Indicator Prediction Summary.

	PLS				LM				
MI 1	RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict		RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict	Dif MAE (PLS- LM)	Dif RMSE (PLS- LM)
GLOBLX03	0.786	0.583	0.050		0.833	0.629	-0.068	-0.046	-0.047
GLOBLX04	0.816	0.643	0.069		0.867	0.678	-0.052	-0.035	-0.051
GLOBLX05	0.789	0.608	0.071		0.816	0.645	0.005	-0.037	-0.028
GLOBLX06	0.846	0.654	0.030		0.905	0.713	-0.111	-0.059	-0.059
GLOBLX08	0.857	0.680	0.046		0.895	0.702	-0.041	-0.022	-0.038
MI 2	RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict		RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict		
GLOBLX03	0.800	0.596	0.051		0.847	0.646	-0.063	-0.050	-0.047
GLOBLX04	0.806	0.625	0.086		0.862	0.664	-0.045	-0.038	-0.056
GLOBLX05	0.777	0.597	0.093		0.785	0.627	0.074	-0.030	-0.008
GLOBLX06	0.826	0.633	0.043		0.878	0.685	-0.080	-0.052	-0.051
GLOBLX08	0.850	0.681	0.043		0.885	0.688	-0.037	-0.007	-0.035
MI 3	RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict		RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict		
GLOBLX03	0.796	0.589	0.052		0.846	0.642	-0.069	-0.053	-0.049
GLOBLX04	0.818	0.642	0.072		0.866	0.669	-0.040	-0.027	-0.048
GLOBLX05	0.765	0.582	0.093		0.791	0.626	0.032	-0.044	-0.026
GLOBLX06	0.833	0.642	0.030		0.886	0.695	-0.099	-0.053	-0.054
GLOBLX08	0.840	0.664	0.055		0.864	0.660	0.000	0.004	-0.024
MI 4	RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict		RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict		
GLOBLX03	0.796	0.589	0.057		0.830	0.620	-0.026	-0.031	-0.034
GLOBLX04	0.819	0.642	0.081		0.867	0.675	-0.031	-0.033	-0.048
GLOBLX05	0.796	0.610	0.090		0.822	0.653	0.030	-0.043	-0.026
GLOBLX06	0.853	0.654	0.026		0.905	0.712	-0.096	-0.058	-0.052
GLOBLX08	0.850	0.678	0.037		0.889	0.696	-0.053	-0.018	-0.039
MI 5	RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict		RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict		
GLOBLX03	0.789	0.581	0.053		0.836	0.631	-0.065	-0.050	-0.048
GLOBLX04	0.819	0.640	0.060		0.872	0.674	-0.067	-0.034	-0.053
GLOBLX05	0.781	0.599	0.094		0.802	0.643	0.044	-0.044	-0.021
GLOBLX06	0.857	0.658	0.026		0.907	0.713	-0.090	-0.055	-0.049
GLOBLX08	0.861	0.682	0.034		0.903	0.701	-0.064	-0.018	-0.042

Notes: PLS: partial least squares path model; LM: linear regression model; RMSE: root mean squared error; MAE: mean absolute error. Dif MAE: PLSMAE-LMMAE. Dif RMSE: PLSRMSE-LMRMSE

MRM1 model PLS predict assessment for full sample of each multiple imputation dataset (MI1 to MI5).
Indicator Prediction Summary.

	PLS				LM				
MI 1	RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict		RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict	Dif MAE (PLS- LM)	Dif RMSE (PLS- LM)
GLOBLX03	0.825	0.653	0.050		0.836	0.654	0.023	-0.002	-0.012
GLOBLX04	0.845	0.660	0.028		0.865	0.678	-0.019	-0.018	-0.020
GLOBLX05	0.807	0.623	0.027		0.819	0.633	-0.003	-0.010	-0.012
GLOBLX06	0.791	0.582	0.039		0.812	0.603	-0.013	-0.021	-0.021
GLOBLX08	0.860	0.688	0.040		0.867	0.682	0.026	0.006	-0.006
MI 2	RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict		RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict		
GLOBLX03	0.821	0.641	0.055		0.835	0.643	0.022	-0.002	-0.014

GLOBLX04	0.832	0,644	0,031		0,847	0,659	-0,003	-0,015	-0,015
GLOBLX05	0.800	0,616	0,040		0,804	0,618	0,031	-0,002	-0,004
GLOBLX06	0.800	0,593	0,051		0,824	0,617	-0,007	-0,024	-0,024
GLOBLX08	0.856	0,693	0,027		0,856	0,672	0,028	0,021	0,000
MI 3	RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		
GLOBLX03	0.831	0,655	0,043		0,838	0,648	0,028	0,007	-0,007
GLOBLX04	0.838	0,649	0,019		0,849	0,663	-0,007	-0,014	-0,011
GLOBLX05	0.790	0,602	0,037		0,799	0,613	0,015	-0,011	-0,009
GLOBLX06	0.800	0,589	0,043		0,828	0,616	-0,024	-0,027	-0,027
GLOBLX08	0.851	0,682	0,030		0,841	0,650	0,052	0,032	0,010
MI 4	RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		
GLOBLX03	0.831	0,656	0,054		0,848	0,662	0,015	-0,006	-0,017
GLOBLX04	0.856	0,666	0,022		0,869	0,681	-0,010	-0,015	-0,014
GLOBLX05	0.816	0,628	0,044		0,829	0,644	0,013	-0,016	-0,013
GLOBLX06	0.796	0,587	0,057		0,820	0,605	0,000	-0,018	-0,024
GLOBLX08	0.858	0,692	0,020		0,862	0,681	0,012	0,011	-0,003
MI 5	RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		
GLOBLX03	0.830	0,653	0,033		0,848	0,660	-0,008	-0,008	-0,018
GLOBLX04	0.859	0,666	0,021		0,878	0,687	-0,022	-0,022	-0,019
GLOBLX05	0.808	0,621	0,031		0,817	0,635	0,008	-0,014	-0,009
GLOBLX06	0.792	0,582	0,048		0,821	0,610	-0,024	-0,028	-0,029
GLOBLX08	0.864	0,692	0,024		0,870	0,682	0,009	0,010	-0,007
Notes: PLS: partial least squares path model; LM: linear regression model; RMSE: root mean squared error; MAE: mean absolute error. Dif MAE: PLSMAE-LMMAE. Dif RMSE: PLSRMSE-LMRMSE									

MRM2 model PLS predict assessment for full sample of each multiple imputation dataset (MI1 to MI5).
Indicator Prediction Summary.

	PLS				LM				
MI 1	RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict		RMSE	MAE	Q ² _predict	Dif MAE (PLS-LM)	Dif RMSE (PLS-LM)
GLOBLX03	0.846	0.656	0.028		0.885	0.698	-0.063	-0.042	-0.039
GLOBLX04	0.789	0.607	0.068		0.803	0.632	0.036	-0.025	-0.014
GLOBLX05	0.815	0.646	0.072		0.849	0.668	-0.008	-0.022	-0.034
GLOBLX06	0.857	0.681	0.046		0.880	0.690	-0.006	-0.009	-0.023
GLOBLX08	0.785	0.581	0.054		0.824	0.614	-0.041	-0.033	-0.038
MI 2	RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		
GLOBLX03	0.828	0.636	0.040		0.863	0.674	-0.043	-0.038	-0.035
GLOBLX04	0.779	0.599	0.087		0.772	0.614	0.104	-0.015	0.007
GLOBLX05	0.803	0.627	0.090		0.842	0.650	0.001	-0.023	-0.038
GLOBLX06	0.849	0.681	0.046		0.870	0.681	-0.004	0.000	-0.022
GLOBLX08	0.795	0.593	0.062		0.835	0.631	-0.035	-0.038	-0.040
MI 3	RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		
GLOBLX03	0.833	0.643	0.031		0.868	0.681	-0.050	-0.039	-0.034
GLOBLX04	0.770	0.586	0.085		0.780	0.614	0.061	-0.028	-0.010
GLOBLX05	0.815	0.642	0.079		0.845	0.654	0.009	-0.012	-0.030
GLOBLX06	0.840	0.665	0.055		0.845	0.646	0.043	0.018	-0.005
GLOBLX08	0.795	0.586	0.054		0.843	0.629	-0.064	-0.043	-0.048
MI 4	RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		
GLOBLX03	0.849	0.655	0.035		0.879	0.691	-0.033	-0.037	-0.029
GLOBLX04	0.798	0.613	0.085		0.802	0.640	0.074	-0.027	-0.004
GLOBLX05	0.818	0.648	0.084		0.855	0.667	-0.002	-0.019	-0.038
GLOBLX06	0.848	0.677	0.045		0.871	0.682	-0.008	-0.005	-0.023
GLOBLX08	0.793	0.587	0.062		0.833	0.617	-0.036	-0.031	-0.040
MI 5	RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		RMSE	MAE	Q²_predict		

GLOBLX03	0.856	0.658	0.027		0.890	0.705	-0.051	-0.047	-0.033
GLOBLX04	0.785	0.603	0.084		0.792	0.631	0.066	-0.028	-0.008
GLOBLX05	0.815	0.642	0.066		0.854	0.667	-0.024	-0.025	-0.039
GLOBLX06	0.856	0.680	0.040		0.876	0.682	-0.006	-0.002	-0.021
GLOBLX08	0.784	0.577	0.063		0.826	0.620	-0.039	-0.043	-0.042
Notes: PLS: partial least squares path model; LM: linear regression model; RMSE: root mean squared error; MAE: mean absolute error. Dif MAE: PLSMAE-LMMAE. Dif RMSE: PLSRMSE-LMRMSE									

Appendix E. Fit results

	DRM	MRM1	MRM2
	SRMR	SRMR	SRMR
MI1	0.077	0.077	0.080
MI2	0.080	0.080	0.083
MI3	0.078	0.079	0.082
MI4	0.078	0.078	0.082
MI5	0.079	0.079	0.082

Appendix F. Direct, indirect and total effects on CA

Type	Path	DRM	DRM	DRM	DRM	DRM	DRM	MRM1	MRM1	MRM1	MRM1	MRM1	MRM1	MRM2	MRM2	MRM2	MRM2	MRM2	MRM2
		Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (M/STDEV)	p-value	LCI 95%	UCI 95%	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (M/STDEV)	p-value	LCI 95%	UCI 95%	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (M/STDEV)	p-value	LCI 95%	UCI 95%
Direct Path	EmergingDeveloped -> CA	0.032	0.055	0.586	0.558	-0.080	0.138	0.033	0.059	0.562	0.574	-0.085	0.148	0.034	0.058	0.584	0.559	-0.082	0.146
Direct Path	Industry dummy -> CA	-0.058	0.089	0.656	0.512	-0.193	0.156	-0.060	0.090	0.669	0.504	-0.196	0.159	-0.056	0.089	0.636	0.525	-0.190	0.156
Direct Path	LogPlantSize -> CA	-0.101	0.057	1.781	0.075	-0.210	0.012	-0.102	0.058	1.760	0.079	-0.215	0.012	-0.104	0.057	1.826	0.068	-0.214	0.009
Direct Path	SC-Ad -> CA	0.213	0.068	3.118	0.002	0.077	0.345	0.207	0.079	2.627	0.009	0.050	0.359	0.178	0.075	2.379	0.017	0.027	0.321
Direct Path	SC-Ad -> SC-Ag							0.500	0.071	7.011	0.000	0.349	0.628	0.651	0.036	18.302	0.000	0.578	0.716
Direct Path	SC-Ag -> CA	0.151	0.068	2.223	0.026	0.019	0.286	0.138	0.076	1.826	0.068	-0.014	0.284	0.124	0.076	1.646	0.100	-0.025	0.273
Direct Path	SC-AI -> CA	0.148	0.054	2.735	0.006	0.044	0.255	0.121	0.064	1.882	0.060	-0.003	0.247	0.191	0.056	3.386	0.001	0.082	0.302
Direct Path	SC-AI -> SC-Ad							0.569	0.045	12.594	0.000	0.473	0.651						
Direct Path	SC-AI -> SC-Ag							0.215	0.075	2.863	0.004	0.070	0.366						
Indirect Path	SC-Ad -> SC-Ag -> CA							0.069	0.040	1.748	0.081	-0.007	0.150	0.081	0.050	1.630	0.103	-0.016	0.180
Indirect Path	SC-AI -> SC-Ad -> SC-Ag							0.284	0.043	6.590	0.000	0.200	0.369						
Indirect Path	SC-AI -> SC-Ag -> CA							0.029	0.020	1.502	0.133	-0.003	0.074						
Indirect Path	SC-AI -> SC-Ad -> CA							0.118	0.046	2.549	0.011	0.029	0.210						
Indirect Path	SC-AI -> SC-Ad -> SC-Ag -> CA							0.039	0.023	1.738	0.082	-0.004	0.086						
Total Indirect	SC-Ad -> CA							0.069	0.040	1.748	0.081	-0.007	0.150	0.081	0.050	1.630	0.103	-0.016	0.180
Total Indirect	SC-AI -> CA							0.187	0.043	4.337	0.000	0.103	0.272						
Total Indirect	SC-AI -> SC-Ag							0.284	0.043	6.590	0.000	0.200	0.369						
Total Effect	EmergingDeveloped -> CA	0.032	0.055	0.586	0.558	-0.080	0.138	0.033	0.059	0.562	0.574	-0.085	0.148	0.034	0.058	0.584	0.559	-0.082	0.146
Total Effect	Industry dummy -> CA	-0.058	0.089	0.656	0.512	-0.193	0.156	-0.060	0.090	0.669	0.504	-0.196	0.159	-0.056	0.089	0.636	0.525	-0.190	0.156
Total Effect	LogPlantSize -> CA	-0.101	0.057	1.781	0.075	-0.210	0.012	-0.102	0.058	1.760	0.079	-0.215	0.012	-0.104	0.057	1.826	0.068	-0.214	0.009
Total Effect	SC-Ad -> CA	0.213	0.068	3.118	0.002	0.077	0.345	0.277	0.067	4.103	0.000	0.141	0.405	0.259	0.065	3.991	0.000	0.129	0.383
Total Effect	SC-Ad -> SC-Ag							0.500	0.071	7.011	0.000	0.349	0.628	0.651	0.036	18.302	0.000	0.578	0.716
Total Effect	SC-Ag -> CA	0.151	0.068	2.223	0.026	0.019	0.286	0.138	0.076	1.826	0.069	-0.014	0.284	0.124	0.076	1.646	0.100	-0.025	0.273
Total Effect	SC-AI -> CA	0.148	0.054	2.735	0.006	0.044	0.255	0.308	0.052	5.877	0.000	0.202	0.408	0.191	0.056	3.386	0.001	0.082	0.302
Total Effect	SC-AI -> SC-Ad							0.569	0.045	12.594	0.000	0.473	0.651						
Total Effect	SC-AI -> SC-Ag							0.499	0.053	9.353	0.000	0.388	0.596						
VAF	VAF SC-Ad -> CA							25.1%						31.2%					
VAF	VAF SC-AI -> CA							60.7%											

Bootstrapping based on n = 5000 sub-samples. LCI, Lower Confidence Interval; UCI, Upper Confidence Interval. VAF, ratio of the indirect-to-total effect